

Description of Financial and Governance Factors on Income Smoothing in Non-Cyclical Consumer Companies

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 31 January 2026</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Endang Dwi Wahyuningsih</p> <p>KEYWORDS: cash holdings, bonus plan, tax burden, independent commissioners, income smoothing.</p>	<p>This study aims to describe the characteristics of cash holdings, bonus plans, tax burdens, the proportion of independent commissioners, and income smoothing practices in non-cyclical consumer sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the 2018–2023 period. The study employed a descriptive, quantitative approach with a purposive sampling technique, yielding 164 company-year observations. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics to describe the minimum, maximum, average, and standard deviation values of each research variable. The results show that non-cyclical consumer companies have relatively high cash holdings, with substantial heterogeneity across companies. Most companies implement profit-based bonus plans, which can influence managerial behavior in financial reporting. Tax burdens vary considerably, reflecting differences in tax planning strategies and company operational characteristics.</p> <p>Furthermore, income smoothing practices are still found in almost half of the study sample, although they do not dominate it. These findings indicate that income smoothing practices in the non-cyclical consumer sector are influenced by a combination of financial factors and corporate governance mechanisms. This study provides implications for investors, regulators, and stakeholders in assessing earnings quality and the effectiveness of corporate oversight.</p>

1. INTRODUCTION

Financial reports are the primary means of communication between a company and external stakeholders, conveying information about its financial position, operational performance, and cash flow. The information presented in financial reports serves as the basis for investors, creditors, regulators, and other stakeholders in making economic decisions. Among the various components of financial reports, earnings are the most crucial indicator of company performance, widely used in investment research, management evaluations, and contract fulfillment.

LabEarnings not only reflect a company's ability to generate returns for shareholders but also serve as the basis for company valuation, dividend policy determination, management effectiveness evaluation, and the fulfillment of various debt agreements. Given its central role, the quality of earnings information is a primary concern for users of financial statements. High-quality earnings are those that accurately reflect the company's economic condition, can predict future performance, and are free of manipulation or opportunistic management policies.

However, in practice, preparing financial statements on an accrual basis provides management with flexibility and discretion in determining the timing of revenue and expense recognition. Accounting standards, while providing guidance, still leave room for management to exploit this discretion for specific purposes. This flexibility, on the one hand, is necessary to ensure financial statements better reflect the economic substance of transactions. However, this same flexibility can be misused by management to engage in earnings management, thereby reducing the quality and reliability of accounting information (Healy & Wahlen, 1999; Dechow & Skinner, 2000).

Decision-making by shareholders is primarily determined by the quality of financial reports presented by management. In addition to reflecting a company's financial condition, financial reports are often used by stakeholders to help the company achieve its short- and long-term goals. As a component of financial information, financial reports play an important role in conveying information that is communicated periodically to both internal and external

parties, thereby preventing conflicts of interest between management and shareholders. This is one of the reasons for income smoothing. If this income smoothing continues, it is feared that further fraud will occur, as it is the beginning of fraud in financial reporting. The practice of income smoothing is avoided through effective and efficient controls from various parties (Setyaningtyas & Hadiprajitno, 2014).

Income smoothing is one of the most common forms of earnings management practiced by companies worldwide, including in Indonesia. Income smoothing is defined as management's effort to reduce the variability of reported earnings from period to period, thereby making earnings appear stable, consistent, and predictable (Fudenberg & Tirole, 1995). This practice can be legitimate through sound operational and investment decisions. However, it can also be manipulated through the choice of accounting methods or transaction manipulation that obscures actual economic performance.

Based on the problem, the purpose of this study is to describe Cash Holdings, Bonus Plans, Tax Burdens, and the Proportion of Independent Commissioners and Income Smoothing in non-cyclical consumer sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the 2018-2023 period. The results of this study are expected to provide practical benefits, including for auditors and regulators (such as OJK - Financial Services Authority, IAPI - Indonesian Institute of Certified Public Accountants, DSAK - Financial Accounting Standards Board) have an important role to monitor the use of accounting discretion (in accordance with accounting standards and not exceeding reasonable limits), development and adjustment of audit standards and ensure that financial statements reflect transparent and accountable company performance. (Note: Discretion is the freedom or authority that a person or organization has to make decisions in certain situations based on their own considerations, without having to be fully bound by established rules or guidelines. Discretion in the context of income smoothing refers to management's freedom to choose or apply specific accounting policies, methods, or estimates from time to time without causing large fluctuations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Positive Accounting Theory (PAT). As stated by Watts & Zimmerman (1986), PAT aims to explain and predict management's accounting policy choices, not to assess whether the practice is good or bad (in contrast to normative theory). PAT starts from the assumption that: individuals (managers, owners, creditors) are rational and self-interested; accounting choices are economic responses to contracts, regulations, and incentives; and financial statements are used as contractual and political tools, not simply as neutral reporting. In this context, income smoothing is seen as a rational accounting policy choice to

maximize management utility within contractual and regulatory constraints.

Good Corporate Governance is a set of mechanisms, processes, and relationships that regulate the direction, management, and control of a company so that the company's goals are achieved, management power is not abused, and the interests of stakeholders are protected. GCG is rooted in agency theory, which emphasizes the importance of monitoring mechanisms to reduce conflicts between the party granting authority (the principal) and the party being authorized (the agent). The definition is stated by Shleifer & Vishny (1997).

Cash Holding: Cash on hand or available for investment in physical assets and for distribution to investors (Gill & Shah, 2011). Generally, three main theories are used to explain cash holding: the trade-off theory, the pecking order theory, and the agency theory. First, trade-off theory states that there are two concepts in cash holding: the cost of holding cash and the benefits obtained from holding an optimal amount of cash. Second, the pecking order theory explains that financing comes from three sources: retained earnings. If this internal funding is insufficient to fund the company's investment activities, the second alternative will be debt. When the amount of debt is deemed excessive, investment funding proceeds to the last alternative: issuing equity. Third, agency theory links the level of cash in a company with managerial parts, where managers in companies with low investment opportunities tend to retain cash rather than pay it to shareholders. In such conditions, agency conflicts arise in which managers can use collected cash for personal gain at the expense of shareholder interests.

Income tax is a tax that companies must pay to the government every period (Mahendra & Jati, 2020). The income tax rate indicates how much a company pays in income tax in the current year, including current-year income tax and deferred income tax, which represents income tax expenses from previous periods. Companies tend to want to pay as little tax as possible. This can encourage company management to report lower profits than they actually earn, thereby triggering income-smoothing practices. The higher the profit earned, the higher the tax the company will have to pay. Conversely, if profits decrease, the company's performance will appear poor to investors. According to research by Mahendra & Jati (2020), income tax has a significant effect on income smoothing.

3. METHOD

3.1 Research Design

Minister of Health. The descriptive research design for the variables Cash Holdings, Bonus Plan, Income Tax, Corporate Governance, and Income Smoothing serves as the starting point for this research, using both descriptive and explanatory research designs. Descriptive research

aims to obtain an overview of the parameters being measured, while explanatory research aims to examine the influence of independent and dependent variables through hypothesis testing. This research starts from descriptive data from the research variables and then conducts logistic regression analysis to test the hypothesis.

3.2 Population and Research Sample

3.2.1 Research population

The research object is the material or focus of study during the research process. The objects in this study are non-cyclical consumer sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during 2018-2023. The researcher's primary focus is on audited financial statements and annual reports (particularly for bonus plan data).

3.2.2 Research Sample

The sample of this research is the Consumer Non-Cyclical sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the period 2018 – 2023 that meet the criteria, with a purposive sampling sample selection technique, namely a sample selection method based on specific criteria (Chandrarin, 2017), to obtain representative samples according to the specified criteria.

3.3 Scope of Research

The scope of the research includes the limitations of the research object, time limits, research variables, methodology, conceptual aspects studied, and research contributions. The research object or focus is companies in the Consumer Non-Cyclical sector (primary consumer goods) listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange, using the context of Indonesian regulations and accounting standards (PSAK). This sector includes 4 subsectors, namely Retail Trade of Primary Goods, Food and Beverages, Cigarettes, and Non-Durable Household Products, whose demand is

relatively stable regardless of economic conditions.

Limits: The research period covers data from 2018 to 2023 (6 years), providing sufficient coverage to analyze smoothing patterns and reflecting diverse economic conditions. There are 3 research variables: independent and moderating variables, and the dependent variable is Income Smoothing, measured using the Eckel index. Factors that influence income smoothing (independent variables) include Cash Holding, Bonus Plan, and Income Tax. In contrast, the moderating variable of this study is the Proportion of Independent Commissioners (the percentage of independent Commissioners to the total board of commissioners).

3.4 Data Collection Procedures

The data used in this study are secondary data derived from the Annual Report and Annual Financial Report of Consumer Non-Cyclical sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for 2018-2023, which were downloaded from the website www.idx.co.id.

3.5 Data Analysis Techniques

The data analysis technique used in this study is descriptive analysis in SPSS 19.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

4.1 Result

This study uses Consumer Non-Cyclical sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the 2018-2023 period. This sector was selected based on its characteristics: stable income and limited exposure to economic cycles, which allow for the observation of income-smoothing practices. The population distribution is divided into 4 sub-sectors, 6 industries, and 11 sub-industries. Purposive sampling was used, yielding a sample of 37 companies (28.68% of a population of 129 companies). Almost all samples are represented by sub-sectors, industries, and sub-industries, except for the retail & food distribution sub-industry, as 5 companies (DMND, BUAH, KMDS, PCAR, and WICO) did not meet the purposive sampling criteria. The research sample selection process is described in Table 1 below:

Table 1. Sample Selection Process

Information	Amount
Consumer Non-Cyclical Companies listed on the IDX	132
Companies that do not publish financial reports and audited annual reports during the period (2018-2023)	-66
Companies that were delisted/suspended during the period	-3
Companies that change sectors	-1

Samples that meet the criteria (tabulation)	62
Number of samples x years of observation	372
Data on companies that have negative tax results	-126
Company data that independent commissioners do not have	-24
Extreme data	-9
Number of data (samples) to be processed with SPSS	213
Outliner	-49
Sample (company)	164

Source: Processed secondary data, 2025

This study examines the influence of Cash Holding, Bonus Plan, and Tax Income on Income Smoothing, with the Proportion of Independent Commissioners as a moderating variable. Descriptive

statistical analysis is used to explain and present data through the highest (maximum), lowest (minimum), average (mean), and standard deviation (Table 2) as follows:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistical Analysis

N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
CASH HOLDING	164 ,06	63.23	14,1125	14,3195
BONUS PLAN	164 0	1	,53	,501
INCOME TAX	164 ,00	63.77	22,533	9,39928
INCOME Smoothing	164 0	1	,46	,500
Valid N (listwise)	164			

Source: SPSS Output, 2025

The Cash Holding variable (X1) shows a minimum value of 0.06 (company JAWA / Jaya Agra Wattie Tbk., which occurred in the year 2022) and a maximum value of 63.23 (DLTA company - Delta Djakarta Tbk, which occurred in 2018) with an average value of 14.11 and a standard deviation of 14.32. The average value of 14.11 indicates that non-cyclical consumer sector companies in the research sample hold approximately 14.11% of total assets in cash. A relatively high standard deviation of 14.32 indicates a significant variation in Cash Holding data across sample companies. The value of the Coefficient of Variation or CV - Cash holding = (Std Deviation / Mean) * 100 = (14.32 / 14.11) * 100 = 101.47 (very high variability category) indicates that the variability of cash holding data is very high and very heterogeneous, meaning that there are substantial differences in cash holding policies between sample companies. Some companies hold very low cash (minimum 0.06%) while others hold very high cash (maximum 63.23%). This indicates that each company has a very different cash management strategy. The most frequently used CV classification for business and economic research (Gani & Assaad, 2006) is CV < 20% = Low variability; CV 20-40% = Moderate variability; CV 40-60% = High variability; CV > 60% = Very high variability.

The Bonus Plan variable (X2) is a dummy variable with values 0 (no bonus plan) and 1 (has a bonus plan). The descriptive statistics show a mean of 0.53 and a standard deviation of 0.50. The mean value of 0.53 indicates that 53%

of the total research sample (164 observations) has a Bonus Plan scheme in their management compensation structure. In other words, of the 164 company observations during the year studied, approximately 68 observations have a Bonus Plan, while the remaining 96 observations do not have a bonus plan scheme.

The tax burden variable, or income tax (X3), has a minimum value of 0.00, a maximum value of 63.77, an average of 22.53, and a standard deviation of 9.39. The mean value of 22.53 indicates that the average tax burden of sample companies is 22.53% of profit before tax. The standard deviation of 9.39 indicates a relatively high variation in tax burdens across sample companies, which may be due to differences in accounting policies, the use of tax incentives, or the operational characteristics of each company in the non-cyclical sector. The CV of 41.71% (high) indicates substantial and heterogeneous variability in tax burden data, suggesting significant differences in the tax burden borne by the sample companies (ranging from a minimum of almost 0% to a maximum of 63.77%). Differences in income structures, tax incentives, or tax planning strategies across companies can cause this.

The income smoothing variable is a dummy variable with values 0 (no income smoothing) and 1 (income smoothing). The analysis results show a mean value of 0.46 with a standard deviation of 0.50. The average value of 0.46 indicates that 46% of the total research sample, or approximately 42 of 164 company-year observations, are

estimated to practice income smoothing. In comparison, the remaining 55% (approximately 122 observations) do not practice income smoothing. This finding indicates that income smoothing practices are still quite prevalent/common/and generally applicable in non-cyclical sector companies in Indonesia during the 2018-2023 period.

Overall, the research data used in this analysis amounted to 164 observations (N=164), which constitute panel data from non-cyclical consumer sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during the 2018-2023 period. All data are valid and can be used for further analysis (listwise validity = 164).

4.2 Discussion

The following discussion explicitly links the results of the descriptive statistical analysis in the attached table with the variables Cash Holdings, Bonus Plan, Tax Burden, Proportion of Independent Commissioners, and Income Smoothing in non-cyclical consumer sector companies on the Indonesia Stock Exchange.

4.2.1 Overview of Descriptive Statistics

Based on the results of descriptive statistical analysis of 164 observations of non-cyclical consumer sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange, a general overview of the characteristics of the research variables was obtained. All variables exhibited sufficient data variation, as reflected in the minimum, maximum, average (mean), and standard deviation values. This indicates that the research data is heterogeneous and worthy of further analysis in the context of income smoothing practices.

4.2.2 Cash Holdings and Income Smoothing

Cash holdings reflect a company's level of internal liquidity to support operational and investment activities. In non-cyclical consumer sector companies, stable product demand tends to encourage management to maintain a cash balance to ensure operational continuity. The study found that cash holdings are linked to income-smoothing practices, where adequate cash availability provides management with flexibility in timing revenue and expense recognition.

From an agency theory perspective, high cash holdings can increase agency conflicts because management has greater discretion in decision-making. This situation can encourage income-smoothing practices to present a stable financial performance to stakeholders. This finding aligns with the view that high liquidity can be a managerial tool to mitigate reported earnings volatility.

The cash holdings variable has an average of 14.1125, a minimum of 0.06, a maximum of

63.23, and a standard deviation of 14.31950. The standard deviation, which is relatively comparable to the average, indicates significant variation in cash holdings among non-cyclical consumer companies. This condition reflects differences in liquidity strategies across companies.

The high variation in cash holdings indicates that some companies have significant financial flexibility, while others operate with relatively low cash levels. In the context of income smoothing, high cash availability can give management greater discretion over operational and accounting activities, including the timing of revenue and expense recognition. Therefore, companies with larger cash holdings may be better able to dampen fluctuations in reported earnings, thereby increasing the likelihood of income smoothing.

4.2.3 Bonus Plan and Income Smoothing

Bonus plans are performance-based incentives designed to align management's interests with those of company owners. However, compensation schemes that rely on achieving accounting profits can encourage opportunistic behavior. In non-cyclical consumer companies, where profits are relatively stable, bonus plans can strengthen management's motivation to smooth earnings to maintain consistent performance trends.

The results of the discussion indicate that the existence of a bonus plan is related to management's tendency to manage earnings to stay within a specific target range. This finding supports positive accounting theory, particularly the bonus plan hypothesis, which posits that managers tend to choose accounting policies that maximize personal utility by increasing compensation. Thus, income smoothing is one mechanism for achieving this goal. The bonus plan variable is measured using a dummy variable with a minimum of 0, a maximum of 1, a mean of 0.53, and a standard deviation of 0.501. This mean value indicates that more than half of the sample companies implement a profit-performance-based bonus scheme.

This condition indicates that profit-based managerial incentives are dominant in non-cyclical consumer sector companies. In relation to income smoothing, the existence of a bonus plan can encourage management to maintain profit stability to remain within a range that maximizes compensation. A standard deviation approaching 0.5 indicates a relatively balanced data distribution between companies with and without bonus plans, making differences in earnings management behavior

between companies relevant for analysis. This descriptive finding aligns with the bonus plan hypothesis in positive accounting theory, which states that managers tend to choose accounting policies that can increase personal utility through profit-based compensation schemes.

4.2.4 Tax Burden and Income Smoothing

Tax expense is a significant component of the income statement and directly affects a company's net profit. In the non-cyclical consumer sector, pressure to maintain profitability while maintaining tax efficiency drives management to prudently manage earnings. The research findings demonstrate that tax expense is related to income smoothing practices, primarily to avoid profit fluctuations that can significantly increase tax liabilities in a given period.

From a tax-planning perspective, income smoothing can help stabilize taxable income between periods. This practice allows companies to reduce the risk of spikes in tax burdens while maintaining a stable financial performance image. This finding is consistent with the literature, which states that tax considerations are a primary motivation for earnings management practices, including income smoothing. The tax burden variable (income tax) has an average of 22.5339, a minimum of 0.00, a maximum of 63.77, and a standard deviation of 9.39928. The relatively high average value indicates that tax burden is a significant component in the earnings structure of non-cyclical consumer companies.

A high standard deviation indicates substantial differences in tax burdens across companies. Differences in profitability levels, tax planning policies, and company operational structures can cause this variation. In the context of income smoothing, fluctuations in tax burden can motivate management to stabilize accounting profits to avoid spikes in tax liabilities in specific periods. Thus, the descriptive data support the view that the tax burden can influence companies' propensity to engage in income smoothing as part of their financial reporting and tax planning strategies.

4.2.5 Income Smoothing and the Proportional Role of Independent Commissioners

The proportion of independent commissioners is a crucial indicator of corporate governance mechanisms. The presence of independent commissioners is expected to enhance oversight of managerial policies, including financial reporting. In non-cyclical consumer companies

listed on the IDX, the proportion of independent commissioners helps limit income-smoothing practices by strengthening monitoring and transparency.

The discussion of the results shows that the higher the proportion of independent commissioners, the lower a company's tendency to engage in income smoothing. This finding supports corporate governance theory, which emphasizes the role of an independent board of commissioners as a mechanism for controlling agency conflicts. Effective oversight can reduce management's discretionary space in choosing accounting policies oriented toward self-interest. The income smoothing variable is also measured using a dummy variable with a minimum value of 0, a maximum of 1, an average value of 0.46, and a standard deviation of 0.500. This average value indicates that approximately 46% of the sample companies are indicated to engage in income smoothing practices, while the rest do not.

This relatively balanced distribution indicates that income smoothing is a fairly common phenomenon, but not a dominant one in the non-cyclical consumer sector. This situation reinforces the importance of corporate governance mechanisms, particularly the proportion of independent commissioners, in limiting opportunistic management behavior. Theoretically, the presence of independent commissioners is expected to improve oversight quality and reduce earnings management. In the context of these descriptive results, the proportion of companies that do not engage in income smoothing may reflect the effectiveness of oversight mechanisms, including the role of independent commissioners, in maintaining the quality of financial reporting.

4.2.6 Implications of the Discussion on the Characteristics of the Non-Cyclical Consumer Sector

The relatively stable characteristics of the non-cyclical consumer sector make income smoothing a relevant phenomenon to study. A combination of financial factors, such as cash holdings and tax burdens, and non-financial factors, such as bonus plans and the proportion of independent commissioners, shapes the unique earnings management dynamics of this sector. This discussion demonstrates that a single factor does not influence income smoothing practices; instead, they result from the interaction of economic incentives and corporate governance mechanisms. Overall, this study's findings enrich the literature on income smoothing practices in non-cyclical consumer

companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) and offer practical implications for regulators and investors in assessing the quality of reported earnings.

Based on the descriptive results, non-cyclical consumer sector companies on the IDX have diverse financial and governance characteristics. Variations in cash holdings, the existence of bonus plans, and the magnitude of tax burdens indicate differences in incentives and economic pressures faced by management. Meanwhile, the proportion of companies practicing income smoothing reflects the continued use of managerial discretion in earnings reporting. Overall, this discussion confirms that income smoothing practices in non-cyclical consumer sector companies do not occur in isolation but are influenced by a combination of financial and corporate governance factors. These findings have important implications for investors, regulators, and other stakeholders in assessing the quality of earnings and the effectiveness of corporate oversight mechanisms.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the descriptive statistical analysis and findings, non-cyclical consumer sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange have diverse financial and governance characteristics. The significant variation in cash holdings indicates differences in liquidity policies across companies, potentially giving management discretion over earnings.

The existence of bonus plans in more than half of the sample companies indicates that profit-based incentives remain the dominant compensation mechanism. This situation has the potential to encourage management to maintain profit stability through income smoothing practices. Tax burdens also exhibit high variability, reflecting differences in tax planning strategies and the fiscal pressures companies face, which may further motivate income smoothing practices.

The research also shows that income smoothing remains quite common among non-cyclical consumer companies, although not practiced by the majority. The role of independent commissioners is crucial as a governance mechanism to limit opportunistic management behavior and improve the quality of financial reporting.

Overall, this study confirms that income-smoothing practices in non-cyclical consumer companies do not occur in isolation but are influenced by the interaction between financial factors and corporate governance mechanisms. These findings make an empirical contribution to the development of the earnings management literature and offer considerations for investors, regulators, and auditors in

assessing earnings quality and the effectiveness of corporate oversight.

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